

THE EU GRANTS TEMPORARY PROTECTION FOR PEOPLE FLEEING WAR IN UKRAINE

Time to rethink unequal solidarity in EU asylum policy

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Abstract

More than two million people have fled Ukraine since Russia's invasion began on 24 February 2022. To respond to the sudden large-scale displacement from Ukraine, the 2001 EU Temporary Protection Directive has been activated for the first time. This paper examines the key issues and questions raised by the EU's temporary protection regime to people fleeing Ukraine, and the medium and long-term issues which can be expected from its implementation. It draws on lessons learned or 'not to be learned' from policies adopted by countries such as Turkey that responded to large-scale displacement from Syria, and others in South America, such as Colombia and Brazil, that responded to large-scale displacement from Venezuela. The paper argues that the solidarity principle enshrined in the EU Treaties needs to be substantially rethought and revisited. People fleeing conflicts and seeking asylum should not be subjected to illegitimate double standards based on their European or non-European origin or any other discriminatory grounds such as race, ethnic origin, and religion. EU asylum policy should be tailored and implemented in a way that upholds the notion of equal solidarity following a human-centric approach, putting every individual's dignity and agency at the heart of its attention. Priority needs to be given to tackling institutionalised forms of discrimination and racism towards non-European asylum seekers and refugees, as these run contrary to the rule of law and fundamental rights principles enshrined in Article 2 of the Treaty on European Union (TEU).

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The cover photo of this paper features the monument of the Archangel Michael located in Kyiv's main square – Mercy Independence (Maidan). The symbol of the Archangel Michael has received various interpretations across different religions and traditions. We chose it as a cover photo because we think that it symbolises integrity, courage and justice for those who have lost their lives or are fleeing the war in Ukraine, as well as for every person who has been (or is) forcibly displaced from non-European countries and seeking protection or refuge around the world. This same integrity and courage stands for the wide mobilisation and compassion expressed by ordinary people and civil society to welcome, support and treat anyone in need with an equal sense of dignity.

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This paper considers all relevant events up until Friday 11 March 2022.

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Executive Summary

More than two million people have fled Ukraine since Russia's invasion began on 24 February 2022. To respond to the sudden large-scale displacement from Ukraine, and in an unprecedented move, the European Commission proposed activating the Temporary Protection Directive and the Council adopted it by unanimous decision on 3 March 2022.

The activation of the Temporary Protection Directive regime is a welcome and positive step towards ensuring solidarity and compassion towards those who are suffering and in need of protection. However, its activation and implementation raises crucial questions calling for careful consideration and reflection, in particular concerning the structural foundations and concepts underpinning the EU's asylum policy, and the principle of solidarity enshrined in Art. 80 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TEU).

This paper examines the key issues and open questions raised by the EU's policy responses to people fleeing Ukraine by focusing on the activation and implementation of the EU temporary protection regime. It argues that the EU solidarity principle should be tailored and implemented in a way that upholds the notion of *equal solidarity* following a human-centric approach, putting every individuals' dignity, agency and the prohibition of discrimination at its heart.

The paper draws lessons by analysing policies adopted by countries such as Turkey to respond to large-scale displacement from Syria, and others in South America, such as Colombia and Brazil, to respond to large-scale Venezuelan displacement. In doing so, it identifies 'lessons learned', and 'not to be learned', and key principles for the EU to consider when implementing the TP Directive and when considering the medium and longer-term issues linked to people fleeing Ukraine and seeking refuge in the EU.

Section 2 examines Russia's aggression in Ukraine and gives a quantitative and qualitative picture of the scale and nature of the forced displacement from Ukraine. This Section highlights the unprecedented compassion shown by a range of actors, including ordinary citizens, at Ukraine's borders. It also includes cases of unequal treatment at EU borders and institutionalised racism towards non-Ukrainian third country nationals, which have been strongly condemned by several United Nations experts and the African Union.

Section 3 focuses on the EU's responses, in particular the activation of the TP Directive and the EU's recent implementation of its external border policy. The TP Directive foresees an immediate group-based protection status granting residence permits to beneficiaries without the need to pass lengthy asylum determination procedures. The paper provides a comparative snapshot drawing the most important differences between the Commission Proposal for activating the TP Directive and the final adopted text of the Council's Decision.

A key finding is that the final version of the Decision gives Member States wider room for manoeuvre when deciding whether to apply or not the TP Directive model to non-Ukrainian third country nationals – including permanent residents in the country – and asylum seekers. We argue that in line with the fundamental right of non-discrimination enshrined in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and international human rights law, *everybody* fleeing Ukraine – including asylum seekers and other third-country nationals – should be admitted to the Union territories and be granted equal access to temporary protection. Such a policy would be also compatible with the legal foundations and political commitments enshrined in the UN Global Compact on Refugees and the UN Global Compact on Migration.

Sections 4 and 5 focus on temporary protection policies outside of Europe and in some of the largest forced displacements receiving countries in the world, namely, Turkey and South America, and aims to draw lessons on ‘what to do’ and ‘what not to do’ when responding to large-scale entries of people looking for international protection. *Section 4* examines how South American countries, such as Brazil and Colombia have responded to Venezuelan displacement, whilst *Section 5* explores Turkey’s temporary protection regime implemented for Syrians since the beginning of the Syrian Civil War. They identify lessons for the EU to learn in the different phases of implementating the TP Directive and designing medium and long-term policy responses focusing on durable solutions, including an effective route for applying for asylum or regularisation, as well as socio-economic inclusion, security of residency and family life of beneficiaries.

Section 6, by building on the analysis and lessons drawn, calls on the EU to rethink the *unequal solidarity paradigm* characterising its asylum, temporary protection, and border policies towards non-European third country nationals. The swift activation of the TP Directive stands in stark contradiction to the lack of common responses and political blockage in response to the large-scale forced displacements from non-European countries such as Libya, Afghanistan or Syria. The Council Decision triggering the temporary protection regime is problematic as it is fully consistent with the position held by some EU Member State governments (including those in Hungary, Poland and Slovakia) to not uphold their legal commitments regarding asylum seekers and refugees coming from African and certain Asian countries and the Middle East, and develop an EU inter-state permanent relocation system moving beyond the one still envisaged in the EU Dublin Regulation.

The paper recommends two key standards for EU coordinated action based on equal solidarity: one focused on *protection* and another one on *non-discrimination*. EU asylum policies must give priority to tackling institutionalised forms of discrimination and racism towards non-European asylum seekers and refugees, as these run contrary to the rule of law and fundamental rights principles enshrined in article 2 of the Treaty on the European Union.

The EU responses to people fleeing the war in Ukraine show that a different asylum policy is realistic and possible, one which calls for reconsidering and rethinking the until-now prevailing nationalistic and inter-state notion of *unequal solidarity offering protection to some and not to all*. People fleeing conflicts and seeking asylum should not be subjected to double standards or discrimination at the EU's borders because of their race, ethnicity or religion or being part of particular social group.

The EU needs to plan ahead and come up with different options which do not undermine the 1951 UN Geneva Convention regime if the Russia-Ukraine conflict persists. The unfair sharing of inter-state solidarity envisaged in the EU Dublin Regulation and its restrictions and criminalisation of so-called 'secondary movements of asylum seekers' should be also reconsidered and abolished.

EU asylum and migration policies need to shift their conceptual assumptions from asylum seekers and refugees as powerless 'beneficiaries' to resourceful human beings. Asylum policies must be at the intersection between the rule of law, democracy and fundamental rights, where the equal dignity of every person prevails for the sake of humanity and justice.

The EU's commitment to help those in need is unwavering. We will live up to our values and receive everyone fleeing Russian aggression with respect and humanity. We will continue to step up the effective delivery of emergency assistance and humanitarian aid. Solidarity is the keystone for the EU as we meet the refugee challenge in the coming months.

[\(Commission Communication, 8 March 2022\)](#)

1. Introduction

Russia's violent invasion of Ukraine is bringing back the human horrors of armed conflict and people forced to flee seeking asylum. The situation in Ukraine brings to the forefront as to what it means to be human with equal dignity, and the crucial role that upholding human rights – and their interconnectedness with the rule of law and democratic principles – have for safeguarding peace.

The invasion commenced on 24 February 2022. In the following days, large numbers of Ukrainians and others previously resident in Ukraine fled directly to various European states. In an unprecedented move, the European Commission proposed the activation of the 2001 Temporary Protection (TP) Directive¹, with EU Member States formally adopting it on 4 March 2022². This is a much welcomed step to ensuring that those escaping war are facilitated safe access to the EU's territory without needing lengthy individual asylum determination status procedures. The activation of the TP Directive sends a clear message of a common EU commitment to implement a coordinated response, avoiding *ad hoc*/unilateral Member States measures, easing pressures on national asylum systems and ensuring a common level playing field of rights for potential beneficiaries fleeing the war.

That notwithstanding, the immediate activation of this EU temporary protection regime brings a series of open question and challenges. This is so in relation to the limited personal scope of beneficiaries which have been envisaged in the final text of the agreed Council Decision, which grants Member States the option not to apply the TP Directive regime to all third country nationals – including permanent residents - and asylum seekers residing in Ukraine. It also relates how EU Member States will implement the directive, as well as the policies which will be devised to address the medium and long-term implications for affected individuals.

¹ Council Directive on minimum standards for giving temporary protection in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof 2001/55, 20 July 2001, OJ L 212/12. See European Commission, Proposal for a Council Implementing Decision establishing the existence of a mass influx of displaced persons from Ukraine within the meaning of Article 5 of Directive 2001/55/EC, and having the effect of introducing temporary protection, COM(2022) 91 final, 2.3.2022, Brussels.

² Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/382 of 4 March 2022 establishing the existence of a mass influx of displaced persons from Ukraine within the meaning of Article 5 of Directive 2001/55/EC, and having the effect of introducing temporary protection, OJ L 71/1.

The swift agreement to activate the TP Directive also stands in stark contradiction with the political blockage by EU Member States over proposals for reforming the EU asylum system which have been on the table since the 2015/2016 so-called ‘European Refugee Humanitarian Crisis’. This political blockage is due in large part to the government positions of states that have an external border with Ukraine, in particular Hungary, Poland and Slovakia. These governments have consistently refused a revamped responsibility distribution model establishing a permanent relocation mechanism and moving beyond the EU Dublin Regulation. These same governments have also being explicit in their refusal to share equal responsibility with other EU Member States in southern Europe and uphold their legal commitments as regards asylum seekers and refugees coming from African and certain Asian countries, and the Middle East.

While the capacity to reach a common EU response is certainly to be praised, this same response raises a critical question: Why is the current situation so different from other recent or still ongoing large-scale forced displacements that the activation of the TP Directive is immediately justified? Or, to put it more bluntly, why is the conflict in Ukraine different from the recent conflicts in non-European countries, such as Libya, Afghanistan and Syria?

The TP Directive has existed since 2001. Despite the many voices calling for its activation to deal with large numbers of refugees arriving to the EU from countries like Syria³, it has never been applied in practice as it was deemed as too ‘politically unrealistic’. The question regarding ‘the novelty’ or specificity of the current situation is truly pertinent. This is so in a context where the responses by some EU Member States possessing EU external borders with Ukraine have shown that the right to leave and to cross borders has not been open for *everybody* fleeing Ukraine.

Instead, the discriminatory and xenophobic life-threatening treatment of non-white third country nationals and asylum seekers from African, Asian and Middle East countries has been documented when exercising the right to flee the violence in Ukraine and to seek asylum in the EU. This shows the persistence of *systemic unequal solidarity* in the EU and Member States’ asylum systems which needs to be understood as a threat to the rule of law enshrined in Article 2 Treaty on European Union (TEU).

So, what are the underlying issues at stake behind the unequal treatment given to Ukrainian nationals in comparison to third country nationals from non-European countries with respect to the newly adopted EU temporary protection regime? The answers to this question are of central relevance when analysing the compatibility of the EU’s responses to forced displacement from Ukraine with the legal human rights and refugee protection standards and

³ In February 2015, Member of the European People’s Party Elisabetta Gardini urged the Commission to draft a proposal for the activation of the Temporary Protection Directive as part of a response to the migration crisis in Europe.” LIBE Newsletter, Issue 7 (20 February 2015); Ineli-Ciger, M. (2016), Time to Activate the Temporary Protection Directive, *European Journal of Migration and Law*, 8, pp. 1- 33, p. 13.

the political commitments enshrined in the UN [Global Compacts on Refugees](#) (GCR) and [Migration](#) (GCM).

This paper argues that the legal foundations of both UN Global Compacts lay an unequivocal obligation by all UN states to respect, safeguard and promote the rule of law and its intersection with fundamental rights and refugee protection. International and EU human rights standards envisage the absolute prohibition of institutionalised forms of discrimination on the basis of race, ethnicity, origin, religion or other related grounds when managing borders and ensuring access to international protection or asylum for *every person* in need.

While the increasing number of people fleeing the war in Ukraine are attracting high political and media attention, it is a crucial time to rethink the structural foundations and concepts underpinning the Union's asylum policy. This is particularly so in respect of the EU solidarity principle enshrined in Article 80 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) and the specific ways in which it can be designed, tailored and implemented in a way which fully upholds and promotes the notion of *equal solidarity*⁴.

This concept not only invites us to reflect on ways in which to ensure inter-state equality in regard to the sharing of responsibility for every person seeking asylum – irrespective of their origin or any other personal characteristic. It also calls for a *human-centric approach* putting individuals' dignity, agency and the prohibition of non-discrimination and racism in EU asylum policies at its heart. And while EU Member States possessing EU external borders with Ukraine have showed clear signs of openness and compassion towards Ukrainian nationals, such openness *must not be 'a la carte'* depending on the attributed cultural or racial affinities of the people fleeing war. It must apply to *all* people equally.

This paper falls within the scope of the Horizon 2020 [ASILE project](#). The project aims to examine the EU's role in implementing the UN GCR and analyse international and regional asylum governance responses to draw lessons learned or 'not to be learned' from other countries and world regions. Therefore, the paper examines the key issues and questions raised by currently existing temporary protection responses adopted by countries such as Turkey or others such as Colombia and Brazil in South America. Is there anything 'there' for the EU to learn from as it implements the TP Directive and when thinking of the medium and longer-term policy responses to the current crisis?

The paper examines the immediate EU policy responses to people fleeing the war in Ukraine⁵, with particular attention given to the specific shapes of the adopted TP Directive. It starts by providing a 'what we know so far' analysis regarding the scale and key issues pertaining to people trying to leave Ukraine in search of international protection in the EU (*Section 2*). The

⁴ On the concept of 'equal solidarity' refer to Carrera, S. and Cortinovis, R. (2019), *The Malta declaration on SAR and relocation: A predictable EU solidarity mechanism?*, CEPS Policy Insight 2019-14, Brussels.

⁵ While there are many crucial challenges related to the basic human right to leave Ukraine, this paper focuses exclusively on the EU responses.

assessment then moves into a study of the EU Temporary Protection regime, comparing the European Commission's proposal with the finally adopted text by the Council of the EU, as well as the Commission's guidelines on easing external border controls (*Section 3*). Next, *Section 4* engages in a comparative analysis of the policy responses and 'lessons learned' – or 'not to be learned' or replicated – by South American countries to the many Venezuelans who have sought asylum within their borders, in particular those from Colombia (*Section 4.1*) and Brazil (*Section 4.2*), as well as those from Turkey (*Section 5*). Based on this analysis, we recommend a set of standards aimed at recalibrating the EU's asylum policy towards a model of equal solidarity in *Section 6* and then the paper's conclusions in *Section 7*.

2. A quick recap on people fleeing Ukraine to the EU: Numbers, humanitarianism, *ad hoc* responses and discrimination

The Russian invasion of Ukraine that began during the early morning of 24 February 2022 has shocked the World. The collective empathy, relatedness and guilt for not being able to defend Ukraine or implement a 'no fly zone' has led European countries to resist with economic sanctions on Russia and embrace humanitarianism towards Ukraine. After initial hesitation, EU Member States found a 'common ground' on a large set of sanctions. Self-interested calculations and positions within the EU were successfully overcome, even in countries such as Cyprus, Germany, Hungary and Italy, who [initially blocked](#) the Russian lock-out from SWIFT among other harsher economic penalties.

In addition, within neighbouring and post-Soviet countries there is a very deep understanding that if Ukraine falls – '[we're next](#)'. For western Europe there is also a sense of guilt as wealthy and powerful countries watch how Ukrainian cities are being bombed from the comfort of their homes, all the while with NATO's hands tied and unable to go to Ukraine's defence. So, humanitarianism is only the second-best option on offer, as the first one – going to Ukraine's defence – is hindered by the fear caused by President Putin's [nuclear threats](#).

People fleeing war-torn Ukraine prompted immediate responses by all relevant European institutions and EU Member States' representatives. President of the Commission Ursula von der Leyen said in a press statement that Ukrainians will be met '[with open arms](#)'. The common European response has been [recognised and praised](#) by President of the European Parliament Roberta Metsola in her opening speech on 1 March 2022 during the Parliament's Extraordinary Plenary Session on the crisis.

Individuals across several countries have shown compassion and wave of protests '*In Solidarity with Ukraine*' demanding a stop to the war, the imposition of sanctions on Putin's regime and to protect civilians. The protests have been impressive, with for instance more than 100 000 people protesting in [Berlin](#) and more than 119 protests [organised](#) across France, as of 6 March 2022. In [Lithuania](#), protests in front of the Russian embassy have been ongoing for a week.

And indeed, civil society and ordinary citizens have been actively volunteering and responding to the needs of fleeing people, from providing blankets, hot meals at the borders, to offering their own homes as a temporary shelter. Humanitarian aid, humanitarian evacuations, the protection of civilians and the creation of ‘safe corridors’ have become ‘no brainers’ and ‘must does’ for many European governments, especially those that share borders with Ukraine. For instance, the Lithuanian Interior Minister has [called](#) for a ‘fixed resettlement mechanism’ accompanied with mandatory inter-Member States relocation.

According to [UNHCR statistics](#), see *Figure 1* below, more than 2.3 million people had left Ukraine as of 9 March 2022. 1 400 000 of all the people fleeing the Ukraine arrived into Poland, followed by Hungary (214 160), Slovakia (165 199), Moldova (82 762), and Romania (84 671). Some of them also headed to Russia (97 098).

Figure 1. Number of people fleeing Ukraine by country (as of 9 March 2022)

Source: Authors' own elaboration based on UNHCR statistics.

The actual number of people who will be displaced is currently uncertain. It will ultimately depend on the escalation and duration of the war. The global UNHCR asylum statistics show that 75 % of people leaving home due to armed conflicts stay in their own country (thus being internally displaced) or flee to neighbouring countries. Despite the large numbers arriving into the EU, a majority of them, at least during the first few days, were not staying in government camps but with friends, relatives or with other ordinary citizens who offered their homes as a safe refuge. For instance, Polish authorities [declared](#) on 28 February that special accommodation arranged specifically for fleeing Ukrainians had hardly been tapped.

However, the situation may change rapidly as 60 % of people fleeing Ukraine have thus far arrived into Poland⁶, thus schools and other public facilities may be needed for temporary housing as number of displaced people continues to rise. As *Figure 2* below shows, it is interesting to note that the Polish authorities had been issuing the most of residence permits for Ukrainian citizens in the EU27 before the war in Ukraine had even started. As of 2020, there were in total of 600 000 first residence permits issued to Ukrainians for various family reunification, employment and other reasons in the EU, with Poland alone issuing around 489 000, followed by Czechia, Hungary, Slovakia and Lithuania.

Figure 2. Number of first residence permits issued to citizens of Ukraine in top 5 EU MS and EU27 – in 2020

Source: Authors’ own elaboration, based on [Eurostat, MIGR RESFIRST](#).

Several issues have emerged in the public eye in respect of the implementation of EU Member States’ responses to the number of attempted entries into the Schengen Area by land. Various media sources have reported, for instance, that EU external border controls aim to confirm everyone’s identity quickly and to run the necessary security checks, and that there were about [70 hour queues to enter Poland](#), [seven hours to cross into Slovakia](#), 20 to 30 hours to get into [Romania](#) and also 24 hours queues to enter [Moldova and varying degrees of queues to Hungary](#).

The UN High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) is assisting in varying ways at different border crossings and on arrival. The Inter-Agency [Regional Response Plan \(RRP\)](#) has been swiftly devised by UNHCR and, in line with the UN Global Compact on Refugees foresees as

⁶ Refer to UNHCR [Situation Ukraine Refugee Situation \(unhcr.org\)](#).

‘partnership approach’ by engaging the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), together with other UN agencies and international organisations such as the Norwegian Refugee Council and Save the Children. They are preparing to meet the needs of an estimated 2.4 to 4 million arrivals by operating on the ground with emergency teams and by providing technical support, including the monitoring of reception capacities, and ensuring the most basic and urgent needs of the arrivals.

Along with the involvement of international organisations, there have been various mobilisations of family, friends, diaspora communities, citizens, various local NGOs, local authorities, companies and even celebrities who are seeking ways to help the numerous civil society organisations operating in Ukraine and at the EU’s external borders to ensure the smooth and dignified reception of people. In Poland, just like in other neighbouring countries people and public transport companies are [giving free rides](#) from the border. Those who have been allowed to leave the country have been met with open arms, for instance in Berlin railway stations where people have been [openly offering](#) rooms so that people have homes instead of being resigned to live in state-run reception camps. In Romania, local authorities, companies and celebrities [joined forces](#) to collect donations to welcome arrivals. AirBnB [announced](#) a campaign to house at least 100 000 refugees for at least 14 days.

A UNHCR [briefing](#) published on 2 March 2022 shows that relevant EU Member States are, for the moment, offering various unilateral or ad hoc ‘solutions’, from temporary permits to wider possibilities to seek asylum. In Poland, new arrivals have 15 days to regulate their status and to apply for temporary protection or to ask officially for asylum. In Hungary, the Hungarian Helsinki Committee has [confirmed](#) that temporary protection is applicable until 1 June 2022. However this decree was pronounced prior to the official triggering of the TP Directive (See *Section 3* below).

Ethnic Hungarians residing in Ukraine have also been [issued](#) with Hungarian cards. In Romania, authorities have been accommodating towards civic hospitality, while prior to the triggering of the TP Directive, they seemed to be [following an ordinary asylum approach](#), providing reception within the major regional asylum reception centres.

Despite the rapidly growing number of arrivals, it seems that only a few official asylum applications have actually been submitted. According to the media (as of 27 February), only 10 people have [asked for asylum](#) in Hungary and 35 in Slovakia.

In Ukraine, and at the EU’s borders, numerous racist and xenophobic incidents have been reported by media and civil society actors due to racial profiling experienced by individuals of colour when attempting to leave the country and enter the EU. Media sources have detailed and provided numerous other accounts from people of colour being subjected to separate

queues and longer waiting periods⁷. A [Lighthouse Report](#) shared numerous incidents that occurred in Ukraine when boarding evacuation trains, or trying to flee the country by other ways.

For instance, [South African students](#) fleeing the country have not been allowed to leave the country and enter the EU alongside other people fleeing Ukraine. At least 1 200 foreign students have been reported to be [stranded](#) in the country. Similar discriminatory treatment has been reported by [African students](#) upon their arrival at the Polish border.⁸ Aljazeera has [reported](#) that despite numerous volunteers offering free rides, people of colour have been cheated by taxis charging exorbitant prices. Besides these incidents, there have been [further challenges](#) with regard to the evacuation and reception of Ukrainian minorities, such as the Roma. Those who do not have biometric passports, or even lack any documentation, are likely to experience difficulties as well, for instance older people, [unaccompanied children](#), in particular those living in the state-run orphanages or persons with disabilities assigned to legal guardians.

Some EU government leaders have also issued discriminatory statements concerning the 'specificity' of the people fleeing the war in Ukraine in comparison to asylum seekers from other African and Asian regions and countries, which illustrates institutionalised manifestations of racism. For instance, the Bulgarian Prime Minister Kiril Petkov [declared](#) that 'These [Ukrainians] are not the refugees we are used to... these people are Europeans...These people are intelligent, they are educated people.... This is not the refugee wave we have been used to ...there is not a single European country now which is afraid of the current wave of refugees.'

This has led some actors, such as the African Union to issue a [statement](#) on 28 February 2022 'on the reported ill treatment of Africans trying to leave Ukraine' where it declared itself to be disturbed by reports that African citizens on the Ukrainian side of the border are being refused the right to cross into the EU. The African Union called for equality of treatment and no discrimination regarding the right to leave Ukraine on the basis of nationality or racial identity, as 'unacceptable dissimilar treatment would be shockingly racist and in breach of international law'.

⁷ See for instance The Guardian (2022), 'People of colour fleeing Ukraine attacked by Polish nationalists', 2 March 2022, available at [People of colour fleeing Ukraine attacked by Polish nationalists | Ukraine | The Guardian](#); see also Bayoumi, M. (2022), 'They are 'civilised' and 'look like us': the racist coverage of Ukraine', *The Guardian*, 2 March 2022; and Tondo, L. (2022), 'Embraced or pushed back: on the Polish border, sadly, not all refugees are welcome', *The Guardian*, available at [Embraced or pushed back: on the Polish border, sadly, not all refugees are welcome | Lorenzo Tondo | The Guardian](#). See also Human Rights Watch (2022), *Ukraine: Unequal Treatment for Foreigners Attempting to Flee: Pattern of Blocking, Delaying Non-Ukrainians*, 4 March 2022, available at [Ukraine: Unequal Treatment for Foreigners Attempting to Flee | Human Rights Watch \(hrw.org\)](#).

⁸ Africanews (2022), *Russia-Ukraine conflict: Africans face racial discrimination in Ukraine*, 28 February 2022, available at https://www.africanews.com/2022/02/28/russia-ukraine-conflict-africans-face-racial-discrimination-in-ukraine/?utm_term=Autofeed&utm_medium=AfricanewsEN&utm_source=Twitter#Echobox=1646055917

This report includes a testimony by a Ghanaian student fleeing Ukraine who said that 'My Nigerian friend told me before I got here; armed guards had ordered us to wait as Ukrainians had to be let through first... Right in front of me, I saw a few buses, which were full of white people'. In addition, a student from Somalia said that 'When she finally reached Poland, she said she was told, "Accommodation at the hotel was only for Ukrainians"'.

In the same vein, United Nations Special Rapporteurs [condemned](#) the aggression of Putin's regime on 28 February 2022 and highlighted that people are now fleeing to safety due to a 'well founded-fear' of persecution, ill treatment or other atrocities resulting in the need for international protection. In addition, UN Special Rapporteurs issued a [Joint Statement](#) on 3 March 2022 expressing their concerns about the treatment of people of African descent and recalled that 'racial preferences in the administration of life-saving services, racial restrictions on freedom of movement, racial differentiation in access to immigration status - violates the prohibition on racial discrimination. This prohibition extends to any treatment, whether it is formal, informal, or *ad hoc*.'

The UN Special Rapporteur on contemporary forms of racism, Tendayi Achiume, also⁹ published a statement condemning racist threats and xenophobia experienced at the EU's external borders and called all relevant government authorities and international organisations 'to ensure safe passage and life-saving protections for *all* people affected by the conflict.'

3. Immediate EU policy responses: Activating the Temporary Protection Directive and easing external border checks

The war in Ukraine gave [new political momentum](#) for the European Commission to propose the activation of the 2001 TP Directive for the very first time. The directive was originally designed in response to the forced displacement following the 1998-99 Kosovo War. The directive has never been put into practice or activated by the EU institutions despite reiterated calls to put it in use in human displacement situations resulting from the so-called 'Arab Spring' in the early 2010s, or conflicts in countries like Afghanistan, Libya or Syria¹⁰.

The TP Directive provides an EU-wide model of temporary protection in the event of a large number of entries of displaced people from third countries – which is labelled by the directive as a 'mass influx' of individuals who cannot return to their countries of origin due to armed conflict or systematic/generalised violations of human rights. It foresees an immediate group-based protection status granting residence permits to beneficiaries. The protection is time-bound for an initial period of one year, which may be extended in six month periods up to two years, and which can be prolonged up to three years in cases where the reasons behind temporary protection persist.

Importantly, Member States cannot offer a lower set of rights in comparison to those foreseen by the directive to the temporary protection beneficiaries. These rights include, among others, immediate access to employment and self-employment activities, housing and suitable

⁹ United Nations Special Rapporteur on contemporary forms of racism (2022), *Ukraine: UN expert condemns racist threats, xenophobia at border*.

¹⁰ Ineli-Ciger, M. (2026), 'Time to Activate the Temporary Protection Directive', *European Journal of Migration and Law*, Vol. 18, No. 1, pp. 1-33.

accommodation, social welfare and subsistence means, equal access to education by minors and family reunification rights (Arts. 12-15).

Moreover, the Directive included an *inter-state solidarity regime* under Chapter VI (Arts. 24-26), envisaging a quasi-relocation scheme including the transferal of persons enjoying temporary protection residence status from one Member State to another ‘subject to the consent of the persons concerned’, and in cooperation with the UNHCR.

The stringent, while at the same time unclear, conditions for activating this directive have constituted crucial reasons behind its non-use. These have included the lack of clear and sound qualitative criteria regarding what qualifies as a ‘mass influx’, or the ultimate decision not trigger the temporary protection mechanism being put in the exclusive hands of EU Member States¹¹. This has come alongside an increasing role granted to a consensus-building (*de facto* unanimity) approach inside the European Council in an area where the correct decision-making rule is Qualified Majority Voting (QMV) by the Council – on the initiative of the Commission¹². The European Parliament is only ‘to be informed’ about the Decision. To this we need to add that its protection-driven logic has until now directly collided with the ‘*contained mobility*’ rationale by both the EU and Member States policy responses to similar refugee, humanitarian and armed conflict situations in non-European countries¹³.

The Commission’s [2020 EU Pact on Migration and Asylum](#) came along a [legislative proposal](#) addressing situation of crisis and *force majeure* in the fields of migration and asylum which has called for repealing the TP Directive, which according to the Pact, ‘no longer responds to Member States’ current reality and needs’. The crisis proposal aimed at tackling some of the above obstacles by [introducing an ‘immediate protection status’](#) shifting the activating role from the Council to the European Commission’s hands¹⁴. Furthermore, while the crisis proposal provides more details as regards what constitutes ‘crisis’, this concept still [remains largely uncertain and ambiguous](#) in scope and fundamentals¹⁵.

The European Parliament’s LIBE Committee [2021 Report](#) on the crisis proposal, with MEP Fernando Lopez Aguilar as Rapporteur, called for replacing ‘immediate protection status’ by

¹¹ Beirens, H., Maas, S., Petronella, S. and van der Venden, M. (2016), *Study on the Temporary Protection Directive*, European Commission, DG Home Affairs, January 2016, Brussels.

¹² Carrera, S. (2019), ‘Tampere Programme 20 Years On: Putting EU Principles and Individuals First’, in Carrera, S., Curtin, D. and Geddes, A. (2020), *20 year anniversary of the Tampere Programme: Europeanisation Dynamics of the EU area of Freedom, Security and Justice*, European University Institute (EUI) Book, Robert Schuman Centre of Advanced Studies (RSCAS), Florence: Italy, pp. 51-64.

¹³ Carrera, S. and Cortinovis, R. (2019), *The EU’s Role in Implementing the UN Global Compact on Refugees: Contained Mobility vs. International Protection*, CEPS Liberty and Security in Europe Series, CEPS, Brussels.

¹⁴ Ineli-Ciger, M. (2020), ‘What a difference two decades make? The shift from temporary to immediate protection in the new European Pact on Asylum and Migration’, eumigrationblog.eu, 11 November 2020.

¹⁵ Brouwer, E., Campesi, G., Carrera, S., Cortinovis, R., Karageorgiou, E., Vedsted-Hansen, J. and Vosyliute, L. (2021), *The European Commission’s legislative proposals in the New Pact on Migration and Asylum*, Study for European Parliament (LIBE Committee), Brussels.

prima facie international protection recognition following the EU Qualifications Directive, and the establishment of a mandatory relocation mechanism. Indeed, the Pact [failed to prove](#) the necessity and value added of this new proposal in comparison to the TP Directive. Surprisingly, the Commission has done a full 360 on its own opinion about the use and validity of the TP Directive when it comes to European asylum seekers.

EU interior ministers dealt with the EU's response to forced displacements from Ukraine at the [Extraordinary Justice and Home Affairs \(JHA\) Council Meeting](#) of 27 February 2022, where the Commission's idea to activate the TP Directive found 'broad support' among EU home affairs representatives. Interestingly, Agence Europe [reported](#) on 28 February 2022 that the Polish government representatives originally considered it unnecessary to activate the directive. This was followed by the publication of the Commission's formal [proposal](#) to trigger the EU Temporary Protection regime envisaged in the TP Directive), which was accompanied by a [Communication](#) providing guidelines to EU Member States on external border controls. These were followed by another [Communication](#) entitled 'European solidarity with refugees and those fleeing war in Ukraine' published on 8 March 2022, which synthesises the range of EU lines of action so far adopted, including humanitarian support through [emergency macro-financial assistance](#).

The Commission proposal was approved by EU Member States on 3 March 2022 in record time, and it was formally [adopted](#) on 4 March 2022. It was reported that few expected the proposal to be adopted so quickly. EU interior ministers were expected to give it the preliminary green light during the morning of 3 March, while Member States officials were supposed to work on the various provisions subsequently. Surprisingly, however, Politico [highlighted](#) on 3 March 2022 how 'EU ambassadors held an emergency meeting on Thursday afternoon where they worked through differences in the text', reaching a finished political compromise steered by the French Presidency of the Council, which was later 'signed off' by the interior ministers.

The decision-making strategy followed a [long-standing malpractice in EU migration/asylum policy](#) by both the previous and current European Commission which seeks to achieve an artificial need for a unanimous vote or 'consensus' among all EU Member States in this policy area.¹⁶ The decision was taken by unanimity voting, even though the text of the directive clearly states that its adoption should be through Qualified Majority Voting (QMV). This paper argues that having all EU governments concerned on board, including countries such as Poland, Hungary and Slovakia, is optimal but this has also meant that important concessions widening Member States' discretion to choose to exclude all third country nationals - including permanent residents - among the beneficiaries of the TP mechanism have been unfortunately included in the final shape of the adopted text.

¹⁶ Carrera, S. (2019), *An Appraisal of the European Commission of Crisis*, CEPS Paperback book, Brussels.

3.1 The Commission Temporary Protection proposal and the Council Decision compared

The Commission Temporary Protection proposal starts by confirming the existence of a ‘mass influx’ as a result of the armed conflict in Ukraine (Art. 1). This is based on UNHCR data showing that more than 660 000 people have fled Ukraine to neighbouring countries including not only four EU Member States (Poland, Hungary, Romania and Slovakia) but also Moldova. The Commission, however, also makes reference to [estimates which have been advanced by UNHCR](#) of a ‘projected’ total refugee population of 4 million or a reference to other ‘estimates’ alluding to a figure between 2.5 million to 6.5 million of possibly displaced persons, based on data used by the so-called EU Migration Preparedness and Crisis Management Network.

The Commission now considers the TP Directive to be the ‘most appropriate’ instrument in the current context so as to ensure a common approach for granting a harmonised set of rights offering an adequate level of protection across the EU and - by limiting the need for potential beneficiaries to apply for asylum – reducing the risks of national asylum processing and reception systems becoming inefficient or ‘overwhelmed’ (Points 7 and 13 of Proposal Preamble).

Ukrainian nationals are visa-free travellers in the EU – on the basis of the [2017 EU-Ukraine visa liberalisation](#) and therefore benefit from free movement rights after being admitted into the Schengen area for a 90-day period. Therefore, the Commission proposal emphasises that this regime allows them to freely choose the Member State where they want to pursue their temporary protection application and join their families, friends, and networks across the EU. The Commission expressly acknowledges that the individuals’ agency emerging from these free movement or self-relocation rights have the positive result of lifting pressure on national asylum and reception systems (Point 14 of the Preamble).

The proposal’s personal scope of beneficiaries included Ukrainian nationals displaced outside Ukraine as of 24 February 2022, third country nationals who are ‘unable to return in safe and durable conditions to their country or region of origin’ and long-term residents in Ukraine, as well as their family members (Art. 1.1.). It proposed to leave it to Member States over whether to consider including people holding refugee status or a pending asylum application in Ukraine. The Commission’s initiative left out other third country nationals residing in Ukraine with ‘the ability to return in safe and durable conditions’ to their country or region of origin.

Groups excluded from the TP Directive would have included, according to the Commission’s initiative, third country nationals ‘who were studying or working in Ukraine on a short-term basis’. The Commission proposed that they should be admitted on ‘humanitarian grounds’, without Member States requiring travel documents and ensuring ‘safe passage’ to their country or region of origin. Furthermore, third country nationals fall squarely within the scope of the accompanying Commission Guidelines for ‘border checks’ outlined below. This strict personal

scope came despite a [clear call](#) by the European Parliament's LIBE Committee to ensure a wider range of beneficiaries and guarantee non-discrimination and equal treatment for *everyone* fleeing Ukraine.

Unlike the Commission Proposal, the personal scope foreseen in the Council Decision leaves a wider room of manoeuvre for Member States concerning the applicability of the TP Directive. The Council Decision has positively extended the personal scope of the TP Directive to non-Ukrainian third country nationals who benefit from international protection or 'equivalent national protection' in Ukraine. Individuals having presented an asylum application in the country or under asylum procedures remain excluded from its scope.

Importantly, as *Table 1* below shows, when comparing the Commission's proposal with the final text adopted by the Council, the final Decision puts additional emphasis on leaving a wide room of manoeuvre in the hands of the Member States over whether or not to exclude all non-Ukrainian displaced persons from EU temporary protection, including long-term residents, giving the possibility to instead apply another 'adequate protection under their national law'. This 'adequate status' would probably be 'international protection applicant' or national humanitarian statuses, with no clear reference to the [2011 Qualifications Directive](#).

In the Decision (preamble para 12), the Council recommends the Member States 'to provide for the protection of stateless persons, and nationals of third countries other than Ukraine, who can prove that they were legally residing in Ukraine before 24 February 2022 on the basis of a valid permanent residence permit issued in accordance with Ukrainian law, and who are unable to return in safe and durable conditions to their country or region of origin.' The Council adds that this protection could be either temporary protection or another form of adequate protection under national law. Since asylum seekers, stateless persons, and third country nationals staying legally in Ukraine, such as students, are missing from the scope of temporary protection, this paper accepts this and sometimes refer to this as 'exclusion'. This is because although the Member States are encouraged to expand temporary protection to stateless persons, asylum seekers, and other third country nationals residing legally in Ukraine who are unable to return in safe and durable conditions to their country or region of origin, there is no obligation to do so and Member States can thus freely exclude third country nationals who have fled Ukraine from the scope of temporary protection.

The resulting picture is one leaving a high degree of legal uncertainty concerning the obligations of relevant Member States possessing an EU external border with Ukraine towards non-Ukrainian third country nationals, which can be expected to lead to inconsistent and potentially discriminatory national approaches.

Table 1. The Personal Scope of the Commission Proposal and Council Decision

	European Commission Proposal COM(2022) 91	Council Decision 2022/382
Personal Scope	<p>Art. 2.1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ukrainian nationals residing in Ukraine displaced as of 24 February 2022 persons enjoying refugee status or equivalent protection, or who were asylum seekers in Ukraine at the time of the events <p>Art. 2.1.b:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Third country nationals or stateless persons residing legally in Ukraine and ‘unable to return in safe and durable conditions to their country or region of origin’. This requirement not applicable to third country nationals who are long-term residents (‘persons who have been legally residing on a long-term basis in Ukraine’) who would directly benefit from temporary protection Preamble 12 ‘However, non-Ukrainian third country nationals or stateless persons who are able to return to their country of origin in safe and durable conditions and who cannot be considered as long-term residents in Ukraine and their family members should not fall under the scope of this Decision...Such persons could include third country nationals who were studying or working in Ukraine on short-term basis...’ 	<p>Art. 2.1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ukrainian nationals displaced from Ukraine on or after 24 February 2022, and residing in Ukraine as of 24 February 2022 (a) Non-Ukrainian third country nationals with international protection status or equivalent national protection in Ukraine (b) Family members <p>Art. 2.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It leaves the option or discretion in hands of Member States as to whether to apply the TP Directive or “adequate protection under their national law” in respect of all categories of third country nationals, including long term residents, in particular to those ‘who can prove that they were legally residing in Ukraine before 24 February 2022 on the basis of a valid permanent residence permit issued in accordance with Ukrainian law, and who are unable to return in safe and durable conditions to their country or region of origin.’ <p>Art. 2.3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It provides an option to Member States to apply the TP Directive (in accordance to Art. 7) to other persons – including third country nationals other than Ukrainians – ‘who were residing legally in Ukraine and who are unable to return in safe and durable conditions to their country or region of origin.’

Source: Authors’ own elaboration.

This means that EU Member States can now choose to exclude all third country nationals and asylum seekers in Ukraine from the finally agreed TPD mechanism and it is ‘optional’ for them to grant temporary protection. In any case, Art. 7 of the TP Directive gives discretion to Member States to extend the temporary protection regime to any person displaced from Ukraine due to the conflict irrespective of what the Council decision stipulates.

Furthermore, and importantly, those EU Member States which eventually decide not to apply the TP regime to third country nationals are in any case bound by the Qualifications Directive¹⁷, which expressly includes ‘internal conflict’ within the definition of serious harm for Member States to grant subsidiary protection status. Furthermore, in a welcomed step, the Commission underlined in its 8 March 2022 [Communication](#) that ‘it is of paramount importance that those fleeing from Russia’s aggression in Ukraine without exception, are treated with full respect and care’.

It has been reported that the personal scope of the TP Directive constituted a decisive issue for reaching unanimous voting inside the Council. According to Politico, the changes on the personal scope were [expressly asked for](#) by Polish authorities and other Member States’ representatives.

Concerning family members, the proposal follows the definition of what constitutes ‘family’ outlined in the TP Directive. The family members mentioned in Art. 15 of the directive [actually includes](#) ‘core family members’ consisting of spouses or unmarried partners in stable relationships (subject to the national legislation of the Member State concerned), minor unmarried children (with no distinction as to whether they were born in or out of wedlock or adopted), and ‘other close relatives’ living together with the family and dependent on the sponsor (Art.1.2)¹⁸. The directive’s definition of family is significantly narrower than the definition of ‘family members’ provided under Art. 4 of the [Family Reunification Directive](#). It should be also noted that this excludes temporary protection beneficiaries as sponsors (Art. 3.2.b), and this means temporary protection beneficiaries do not have the right to family reunification under the Family Reunification Directive.

The TP Directive’s narrow definition of family is one of the Directive’s many peculiarities and weaknesses. For instance, it allows Member States to give priority to EU citizens, EEA citizens, and legally resident third country nationals who receive unemployment benefits over temporary protection beneficiaries in terms of access to the labour market. Moreover, the directive also does not clarify which procedures will apply in relation to granting of temporary protection status and includes phrases such as ‘mount a legal challenge’ instead of the ‘right to appeal’ in the context of appealing an exclusion decision.

These peculiarities are a result of the directive belonging to a different era where the EU had different legal competences in the Treaties and migration policy priorities. The TP Directive pursues ‘minimum standards’ at a time when certain rights were not recognised as relevant for the protection of displaced persons in ‘mass influx situations’. The TP Directive being the first EU Directive adopted on asylum matters means that there are significant gaps which need to

¹⁷ Refer to Arts. 15 and 18 of the EU Qualifications Directive. According to Art.15.c serious harm consists of ‘serious and individual threat to a civilian’s life or person by reason of indiscriminate violence in situations of international or internal conflict’.

¹⁸ Peers, S. (2022), ‘Temporary Protection for Ukrainians in the EU? Q and A’, *EU Law Analysis Blog*.

be filled in by the EU and the Member States. However, this does not lower the value of the directive as a key instrument to deal effectively with the current large-scale displacement from Ukraine.

Furthermore, and importantly, Point 15 of the Commission Decision proposal stipulated that while TP status is complementary with national temporary protection schemes, national schemes must not be 'less favourable' with regard to the set of rights foreseen in the directive. The Commission Temporary Protection Proposal also envisaged provisions calling for the exchange of information and the coordination and monitoring of Member States' reception capacities through a so-called 'Solidarity Platform' coordinated by the Commission (Art. 3). This is now enshrined in Paragraph 20 of the Council Decision Preamble¹⁹. A key role is also envisaged for EU agencies Frontex (the European Border and Coast Guard), the European Union Asylum Agency (EUAA) and Europol, with the possibility to provide operational support to those Member States which request it.

According to information provided by the [Commission](#), as of 8 March 2022, a first group of 49 Frontex staff were deployed to EU-Ukraine borders and 162 staff to Romania. Europol seems to already be present in Slovakia and Poland. Similarly, the EU Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA) has been visiting external border crossing points and reception centres in Member States responsible for border management at the EU external frontiers with Ukraine.

Before the publication of the Council Decision in the EU's Official Journal, Agence Europe [reported](#) on 3 March 2022 that other additional agreements between Member States included the non-application of Art. 11 of the TP Directive, so as to allow people to move freely within the EU. This is indeed reflected in paragraph 15 of the Council Decision Preamble which stipulates Member States' agreement not to apply this provision and allow individuals' agency in exercising intra-EU mobility. Art. 11 stipulates that 'a Member State shall take back a person enjoying temporary protection on its territory if the said person remains on, or, seeks to enter without authorisation onto, the territory of another Member State during the period covered by the Council Decision'.

Agence Europe additionally reported in the same article that the Polish and Hungarian authorities had chosen not to activate the above-mentioned *inter-state solidarity regime* under Chapter VI (Arts. 24-26) of the TP Directive and 'to ask for help from their partners in hosting refugees for the time being, a situation that has also puzzled some delegations.' This shows a consistent and persistent opposition of these governments to the wider idea of intra-EU 'relocation' of TP beneficiaries and asylum seekers more generally.

¹⁹ Paragraph 20 of the Council Decision states that, as of 4 March 2022, 'based on the information reported by a few Member States in the context of the EU Migration Preparedness and Crisis Management Network, reception capacities, over and above the absorption capacity of the Ukrainian diaspora residing in the Union, exceed 310 000 places.'

3.2 EU external border checks

As introduced in *Section 2* above, UNHCR has documented how people fleeing Ukraine have experienced long queues at several EU external borders. Overall, however, the response until now by relevant EU Member States (Poland, Hungary, Romania and Slovakia) has been one of, according to UNHCR, ‘open and welcoming borders’ for Ukrainian nationals and their families. A border control and security rationale is still present in the above-mentioned Communication providing guidelines to EU Member States on external border controls.

The Guidelines aim to assist Member States possessing an EU external border with Ukraine (Poland, Slovakia, Hungary and Romania) to facilitate ‘flexibility’ when conducting external border controls under the [Schengen Borders Code \(SBC\)](#). The Commission Guidelines do not provide however any substantive justification concerning the actual necessity and proportionality of ‘external border controls’ when dealing with the situation in Ukraine. It also doesn’t refer to Member States’ fundamental rights obligations under EU borders and asylum law to ensure access to protection and to not expel anyone coming from Ukraine.

As a list of possible measures to be taken, the Guidelines propose, for instance, simplifying border controls for only certain categories of persons. They ‘strongly recommend’ however the concerned Member States to make use of EU agencies (Frontex, EUAA and Europol) in the identification (including nationality screening) and checks of travel documents and Covid-19 vaccination certificates. It also envisaged the use of EU databases, such as Eurodac and SIS II for registration and fingerprinting. The Guidelines even provide for the possibility for Europol to engage in ‘second-line checks’. The negative practical repercussions concerning simplifying border checks through the involvement of EU agencies, checks on vaccination certificates and the use of EU databases have not been duly considered or evaluated.

The Commission puts national border guards and authorities in a rather difficult position by calling them to consider relaxing ‘border controls’ to certain groups of travellers depending on their citizenship or residence status of an EU Member State, the nationality of the traveller or residence status in Ukraine, the ‘vulnerability’ of individuals, as well as information on ‘security threats’, the possession of a biometric passport and a valid travel document, or the status of the person concerned as a ‘key worker’ (e.g. a transport worker proving their profession). In cases of doubt regarding a person’s identity, the Commission recommends border guards to carry out regular border checks.

This may led to a situation of discrimination and fragmentation of national border practices and the application of different understandings of these criteria depending on which border people find themselves at, which can be expected to not necessarily reduce queues and the time for

border checks to take place in practice²⁰. Moreover, the Commission Guidelines forget to mention that the SBC is clear with regard to the point that borders controls must be exercised without prejudice to refugees and people requesting for international protection (Art. 3.b SBC), and that Member States have an unequivocal obligation to carry out EU border controls and surveillance in full compliance with international protection and *the non-refoulement* principle.

There is a sound risk that non-Ukrainian third country nationals residing in Ukraine will be disproportionality targeted by these checks. The Commission's TP Proposal and the finally adopted text of the Council Decision examined in *Section 3.1*. leave too much discretion to national authorities to assess the extent to which third country nationals 'are unable to return in safe and durable conditions to their country or region of origin'. The Guidelines provide no specifications concerning the exact ways in which national authorities are or will be checking the existence of this criterion, thus unlocking the possibility to apply the TP regime or not. Concerning the implementation of returns, the [Commission reports](#) that countries such as India, Morocco, Tunisia and Egypt 'have already worked with Member States to support repatriation of their nationals'.

In particular it is concerning how the specific ways in which 'safety' and 'durability' will be properly and fairly examined on an individual basis in a manner which is not discriminatory and fully complies with the right to seek to asylum by [halting illegal push backs](#) to countries like Belarus²¹. It is indeed also concerning that the Guidelines leave it 'optional' to Member States to provide asylum ('humanitarian protection' in the Commission's words) to non-Ukrainian third country nationals fleeing from Ukraine but not fulfilling the conditions laid down in Art. 6.1 SBC.

4. What lessons can be learned from Venezuela's large-scale displacement?

The way South American countries have responded to Venezuelan displacement may give hope and inspiration for the EU when looking ahead on how to handle arrival of asylum seekers from neighbouring Ukraine. The EU should also not repeat the mistakes we have witnessed since 2015, especially the overwhelming focus of EU and Member States' policies on containment, externalisation and the criminalisation of solidarity.

UNHCR statistics visualised in *Figure 3* below show that the majority of Syrians were also mainly hosted in four neighbouring countries: Turkey (3.7 million), Lebanon (0.9 million), Jordan (0.7 million) and Egypt (0.1 million). As of 2021, all 27 EU Member States are hosting only a bit more

²⁰ Furthermore, in the name of 'potential security issues created at the border by a mass influx of Ukrainians', the Commission's Guidelines recommend Member States to 'alternatively or cumulatively' carrying out these border checks not at external border crossing points, but at a 'safe location away from the border'.

²¹ Carrera, S. (2021), *Walling off responsibility? The Pushbacks at the EU External Borders with Belarus*, CEPS Policy Insight, No. 2021-18, Brussels.

than one million Syrian refugees. In the EU as of mid-2021, the three major hosting countries for Syrian refugees were: Germany (0.7 million), Sweden (0.1 million) and Austria (0.06) million as shown in Figure 3 below. These numbers put current estimations or projections of people fleeing Ukraine into stark perspective.

Figure 3. Distribution of Syrian refugees under the UNHCR mandate in the top five EU countries and top four in the Middle East

Source. Authors' own elaboration based on selected UNHCR data [here as of mid-2021](#).

Some of the EU Member States with external borders with Ukraine have been persistently unwilling to provide access to asylum to refugees and asylum seekers from non-European countries such as Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq and elsewhere. Previous EU responses to asylum seeking mobility from African and Asian countries has shown that a 'closed borders' policy, mandatory waiting periods within massive state-run asylum reception centres hidden from the public, *de facto* detention and limiting and criminalising the free movement of asylum seekers and refugees within the EU are not and should not be seen as dignified and human-centric options in EU asylum policies.

Some South American countries have shown that another policy is indeed possible: one embedded in keeping borders open, ensuring free movement within the country, granting agency to individuals and granting the immediate right to work. As of mid-2021, more than 4.7 million Venezuelans were being hosted by neighbouring countries in South America. There has been a high variation in state responses across South America, however, often due to political relations with the Maduro regime.

While at the beginning of the humanitarian crisis, the [immediate responses](#) by most South American countries were welcoming and adopted an open-door approach²², these policy responses started changing when it became clear that Venezuelan forced displacement was not ‘temporary’ and then [the region was badly hit by the Covid-19 crisis](#), fuelling concerns about the distribution of limited resources. The [result](#) of these ‘mixed’ policies is that currently most Venezuelan nationals residing in other South American countries have an irregular status or are on temporary visas and residence permits²³.

However, and even in the midst of the pandemic, some of the main receiving countries, such as Colombia and Brazil, kept their borders largely open and adopted medium and longer-term regularisation schemes. This sends a clear message to EU policymakers to waste no time in making medium and long-term plans for a post-TP Directive phase, where allowing equal and fair access to asylum procedures and/or regularisation will have to be central policy options.

Despite these ‘uneven’ policy responses, South America has some of the most progressive and liberal migration and refugee legislation in the world²⁴, as is explored below through the cases of Colombia and Brazil. This progressive legislation and policies partly explain the initial ‘welcoming’ response and the persistence of an open-door approach in some of the countries. In comparison with Europe, South American countries have agreed on a more generous and broader definition of ‘who qualifies as a refugee’, and recognised that due to generalised conflicts, including political, economic and social instability, people may also have refugee protection needs. Article 1.2 of the 1951 Refugee Convention, which guides the EU legal asylum and refugee regime, provides a rather narrow definition of ‘refugee’ as individuals fleeing the ‘well-founded fear of persecution on the basis of race, religion, nationality, political opinion or a being part of a particular social group’.

The [Cartagena Declaration on Refugees](#) signed in 1984²⁵ responded to persistent economic crisis, poverty and insecurity that had arisen in Central America, as well as the longer-term experience with forcibly displaced persons and the adoption of political asylum as a response²⁶. The Cartagena Declaration, Conclusion No. 3, thus extended the definition of refugee to those

²² Selee, A. and Bolter, J. (2020), *An Uneven Welcome: Latin American and Caribbean Responses to Venezuelan and Nicaraguan Migration*, Migration Policy Institute (MPI), February.

²³ Brumat, L. (2022), *Migrants or refugees? ‘Let’s do both’. Brazil’s response to Venezuelan displacement challenges legal definitions*, Migration Policy Centre (MPC), European University Institute (EUI), Florence.

²⁴ Jubilut, L. L., Vera Espinoza, M. and Mezzanotti, G. (eds), ‘Latin America and Refugee Protection: Regimes, Logics and Challenges’, *Forced Migration*, Vol. 41.

²⁵ See Rodrigues, G. M. A. (2021), ‘South America and the Cartagena Regime: A Comprehensive Approach to Forced Migration Responses’, in Carrera, S. and Geddes, A. (eds.) *The EU Pact on Migration and Asylum in light of the United Nations Global Compact on Refugees: International Experiences on Containment and Mobility and their Impacts on Trust and Rights*, pp. 1157-169, Florence: European University Institute.

²⁶ Freier, F. (2015), ‘A Liberal Paradigm Shift?: A Critical Appraisal of Recent Trends in Latin American Asylum Legislation’, *International Refugee Law Series*, No. 3, Brill Nijhoff.

who ‘who have fled their country because their lives, safety or freedom have been threatened by generalized violence, foreign aggression, internal conflicts, massive violation of human rights or other circumstances which have seriously disturbed public order.’

The Cartagena Declaration was supplemented by a series of declarations and action plans including: the [San Jose Declaration on Refugees and Displaced Persons](#) (1994), the [Mexico Plan of Action](#) (2004), the [Brasilia Declaration on the Protection of Refugees and Stateless Persons in the Americas](#) (2010), and the [Brazil Declaration](#) (2014). Today, more than 15 Latin American states have transposed the broad refugee definition as provided in the Cartagena Declaration into their national legislations.

The incorporation of the expanded refugee definition into the national legislation of so many countries in the region illustrates the relevance and importance of the Cartagena Declaration in leading a progressive development of international refugee law in Latin America. An *inclusory understanding of refugeehood* is also secured in the Cartagena Declaration by covering situations such as foreign aggression and internal conflicts, both of which are of central relevance to Ukraine.

Brumat and Freier (2021) have noted that in comparison with the EU, South American countries ‘on average are more progressive regarding the scope of protection and the socio-economic integration of both asylum seekers and refugees²⁷’. They quote the findings of Freier and Gauci (2020) highlighting that ‘Argentina, Brazil, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Nicaragua, and Mexico surpass EU protection standards²⁸’. In the case of Venezuelan large-scale displacement, Brazil is the [only South American country](#) that has applied the Cartagena definition to significant numbers of Venezuelan nationals²⁹.

When presented with the large-scale displacement of Venezuelans fleeing massive violations of human rights, serious limitations in the provision of social services, economic insecurity and poverty created by Maduro’s regime, the neighbouring South American countries became even more creative and adopted several different policy responses to large-scale Venezuelan displacement. Policy responses can be [classified into two groups](#): ‘Atlantic+Colombia’ and ‘Andean’.³⁰ The first group has adopted more ‘creative’ policy approaches, including the use of

²⁷ Brumat, L. and Freier, L. F. (2021), ‘South American De Jure and De Facto Refugee Protection: Lessons From The South’, in Carrera, S. and Geddes, A. (eds.) *The EU Pact on Migration and Asylum in light of the United Nations Global Compact on Refugees: International Experiences on Containment and Mobility and their Impacts on Trust and Rights*, pp. 134-143, Florence: European University Institute.

²⁸ Freier, F.L. and Gauci, J.-P. (2020), ‘Refugee Rights Across Regions: A Comparative Overview of Legislative Good Practices in Latin America and the EU’, *Refugee Survey Quarterly*, 39(3), pp. 321–362.

²⁹ Brumat, L. (2022), *Migrants or refugees? ‘Let’s do both’. Brazil’s response to Venezuelan displacement challenges legal definitions*, Migration Policy Centre (MPC), European University Institute (EUI), Florence.

³⁰ Brumat, L. (2022), *Gobernanza migratoria en Suramérica en 2021: respuestas a la emigración venezolana durante la pandemia*, Fundación Carolina, Análisis Carolina nº 12.2021.

the [MERCOSUR Residence Agreement](#) (MRA) to provide two-year residence permits (by Argentina, Brazil and Uruguay), while, as explained below, Colombia adopted a 10-year residence permit. The neighbouring Latin American countries provided safe and orderly avenues for Venezuelans to come into the region by keeping their own borders open. The [Inter-Agency Co-Ordination Platform for Refugees and Migrants from Venezuela](#) has been created to coordinate the different practices, approaches and statistics across South and Central America and the Caribbean.

UNHCR statistics outlined in *Figure 4* below show the distribution among the five major hosting countries in the region. 1.7 million Venezuelans are hosted by Colombia alone, making Colombia the second biggest host country of forcibly displaced persons in the world after Turkey. It also shows that the overall distribution, including other asylum seekers and refugees, that Colombia is followed by Peru, Chile, Ecuador, Brazil and others.

Figure 4. Statistics for Venezuelans only in five major hosting countries in South America by type of protection

Source. Authors' own elaboration based on selected [UNHCR Statistics of mid-2021](#).

4.1 What has Colombia done differently?

Colombia, a country with a population of 50.6 million, thus similar to the population of Spain, has been hosting around [two million Venezuelans](#). This puts the current statistics and estimated projections of people fleeing the war in Ukraine into stark perspective. Initially, Venezuelans who arrived in Colombia were admitted on a Special Stay Permit (*Permiso Especial de Permanencia*) for two years. Among other considerations, the limited period had the effect of leaving many Venezuelan nationals undocumented. Banulescu-Bogdan and Chaves-González

(2021) comment,³¹ ‘by the end of 2020, 56 % of Venezuelan arrivals were in irregular status, limiting their access to services such as education, health care, and banking and crucially, keeping them out of the formal labour market.’

[Current estimates](#) talk about two million Venezuelans that have arrived and/ or continue to reside in the country. The Colombian government reconsidered regularisation and moved from an *ad hoc* or temporary solution to a longer term and strategic approach due to human rights and also pragmatic considerations. Following this reasoning, Venezuelan nationals would keep crossing the borders and, given humanitarian and geographical considerations, it would not be realistic to try to stop them. Consequently, regularisation would enable Venezuelans to contribute to the receiving society, while at the same time, it expands their rights and reduces their precariousness.

To achieve this aim, the Colombian government launched the Temporary Protection Statute for Venezuelan migrants (TPSV) in February 2021. Colombian President Ivan Duque [announced](#) that ‘this mechanism allows us to have information to grant them immigration status and, in 10 years, the possibility of a resident visa.’ It set the precedent by providing Venezuelans with a long-term perspective to rebuild their livelihoods and to avoid the pitfalls of administrative limbo or legal uncertainty and, crucially, gave them access to the formal labour market. In addition, the ‘protective’ status came along with the equal access to healthcare, social assistance and other essential services.

However, [concerns have been raised](#) regarding the meaning and content of ‘protection’ in the TPSV and Colombia’s resources to provide effective access to social services. Such an approach, however, promotes human rights while also stressing state control. The Colombian Temporary Protection Statute, if successful, ‘can extend access to rights to hundreds of thousands (if not millions) of people³². And indeed, it can serve as guidance for the EU when choosing between *enforced temporality and precarity*, or opening up possibilities for medium and long-term planning and meaningful socio-economic inclusion and security of residence. As the Colombian approach acknowledges, people will keep crossing borders and look for protection abroad. Providing them with a regular status that increases their access to rights is therefore the most feasible policy choice.

³¹ Banulescu-Bogdan, N. and Chaves-González, D. (2021), *What Comes Next Now that Colombia Has Taken a Historic Step on Migration?*, Migration Policy Institute (MPI).

³² Brumat, L. (2022), *Migrants or refugees? ‘Let’s do both’*. *Brazil’s response to Venezuelan displacement challenges legal definitions*, Migration Policy Centre (MPC), European University Institute (EUI), Florence.

4.2 Lessons learned from Brazil: Conditional residence rights vs. protection needs?

Brazil is the country that has the highest regularisation rate of Venezuelan nationals in South America (74 % compared to an average of 45 %). This is because Brazil currently provides migratory and refugee status as venues for regularisation, independent from the reasons that motivated people to leave Venezuela. The Brazilian case shows that, in a context of limited capacities to deal with the large-scale arrival of displaced individuals, the reasons why these people fled their country became less relevant and providing them with a regular status was the priority. This policy approach has been the result of a combination of factors including structural conditions, mainly bureaucratic capacities for processing large numbers of asylum applications, as well as the influence of actors such as UNHCR and the United States.

In 2017, the National Immigration Council (CNIg) presented an *ad hoc* solution for Venezuelans who arrived in Brazil by adopting Resolution No. 126, which extended *de facto*, the provisions of the Mercosur Residence Agreement to Venezuelan nationals (despite the fact that Venezuela did not ratify the Agreement). In this way, Venezuelans were issued temporary residence cards. In 2019, the National Committee for Refugees (CONARE), the state, civil society and international organisations closely cooperated and managed to fast-track and expand the recognition of being refugees and asylum seekers to large numbers of Venezuelans. In this way, a significant number of Venezuelan nationals obtained access to protection from subsequent expulsions and were granted rights to access public services and social assistance.

The residence permit has both its upsides and downsides. On the upside, the issuance of the card was swift and it gave the right to seek employment immediately. On the downside, those permits are valid for only two years and subsequent prolongation is dependent on finding employment or proving a means of subsistence. This means that longer-term regular status in Brazil is dependent on individuals' economic and labour situation. The second 'option' is to apply for refugee status. Medina Araujo (2021), alongside numerous Brazilian scholars, has criticised that such *ad hoc* solution fails to offer '...a path to regularisation'.³³

Thus, after a two-year period people could potentially be deported. This regularisation procedure is not *complementary*, but rather substituting or replacing the asylum procedure. This means that the individuals who opted for a residence permit through the Mercosur Agreement cannot apply for asylum. ASILE project research³⁴ has shown that this choice often depends on the willingness to be able to travel back to Venezuela more freely, as individuals holding refugee status must ask for a special permit to do so. The length of the refugee admission process is another influencing factor. At the same time, the residence card has an economic cost that can be too high for most individuals, whereas the process for refugee status is free.

³³ Medina Araujo, N. (2021), 'ASILE Country Fiche Brazil', Available at [Country-Fiche BRAZIL Final Pub.pdf \(asileproject.eu\)](https://asileproject.eu/Country-Fiche_BRAZIL_Final_Pub.pdf)

³⁴ Brumat, L. (2022), *Migrants or refugees? 'Let's do both'. Brazil's response to Venezuelan displacement challenges legal definitions*, Migration Policy Centre (MPC), European University Institute (EUI), Florence.

Despite the progressive character of the migration and refugee policies, there are many implementation challenges. Leitao, working in Sao Paulo with displaced Venezuelans and other refugees, [has explained](#) that the right to work may not necessarily lead to *actual and decent work*, as there are a number of practical obstacles. ASILE project research has shown that most policymakers regard socio-economic inclusion as the main implementation challenge. For instance, many people are still expected to learn Portuguese, or struggle to get their diplomas and professional qualifications legally recognised. Some of them are under precarious labour contracts, and need social assistance, due to, for example, difficulties in finding or paying for housing due to increased prices or they have encountered difficulties to find available places in the education system.

5. Lessons Learned from Turkey

Turkey currently hosts the [largest refugee population in the world](#), including 3.7 million Syrians under temporary protection and over 330 000 international protection status holders and asylum-seekers of other nationalities. Turkey has been implementing a temporary protection policy since 2011 to protect Syrian refugees, and over time has developed its own national legislative framework regulating different aspects of temporary protection. There are crucial lessons that can be drawn from Turkey's experience.

The first lesson relates to the right to work of temporary protection beneficiaries. Although the Syrian influx began in 2011, Turkey introduced the right to work for temporary protection beneficiaries in [January 2016](#). The 2016 Regulation on Work Permit for Foreigners under Temporary Protection, adopted on 15 January 2016, allowed temporary protection beneficiaries access to the Turkish labour market, and Syrians who are working as seasonal workers in agriculture and livestock businesses became exempted from having to apply for a work permit. Prior to the adoption of the 2016 Regulation, Syrians working illegally as low-skilled labourers were paid well below the Turkish minimum wage, thus the introduction of the right to work and the stipulation in the new legislation that Syrians should be paid at least the minimum wage in Turkey [signified](#) a change for the better.

Nevertheless, the work permits issued to Syrians remain quite low; for instance, according to the Turkish government between 2016 and 2019, [only a total of 132 497 work permits](#) were issued to Syrians in Turkey.³⁵ There are many reasons as to why the number of issued work permits to Syrians remains low however, that being the fact that only employers can apply for work permits on behalf of Syrian employees, as well as difficult and prolonged procedures and additional fees exacerbating the problem³⁶. The lesson which can be drawn from here is that

³⁵ Ineli-Ciger, M. (2017), 'Protecting Syrians in Turkey: A Legal Analysis', *International Journal of Refugee Law*, Volume 29, Issue 4, pp. 555-579.

³⁶ Ibid, pp. 561, 562.

although granting the right to work to temporarily protected persons is crucial, it is also necessary to make sure this right can be accessed in practice.

Turkey was too late in introducing a right to work for temporarily protected persons and consequently, Syrians were unable to legally work for five years and many high skilled Syrians left Turkey (Ineli-Ciger, 2018)³⁷. Art. 12 of the TP Directive obliges EU Member States to authorise ‘persons enjoying temporary protection to engage in employed or self-employed activities.’ However, the Turkish case shows that the sooner the temporary protection beneficiaries are given access to the labour market and can obtain work permits without complicated procedures and additional fees, the better.

The second lesson relates to ‘thinking ahead’ and being prepared for the possibility that the armed conflict that created the displacement continues for longer than expected. Turkey opened its borders to Syrians fleeing the war in 2011 and pursued an ‘open-door policy’ for many years. However, many Turkish government officials including the Turkish Prime Minister at the time, Ahmet Davutoğlu, thought the war in Syria would end and Syrians would be able to return to Syria [after a few months if not weeks](#).

Therefore, temporary protection regimes should be time-limited and ideally, they should not continue more than three years.³⁸ Turkish temporary protection is now going on for nearly 11 years. The Turkish government did not have a long-term plan when the Syrian displacement began and it still grants Syrians ‘temporary protection status’. Although the rights and entitlements of the temporary protection beneficiaries expanded over the years, the Turkish temporary protection policy should have been terminated long before 2022. Considering this, a second lesson that can be drawn from the Turkish example is temporary protection is a time-limited response, and it should not continue for more than a reasonable period of time.

It is crucial for the EU to have a long-term plan to be ready to terminate temporary protection and ensure full socio-economic inclusion of TP beneficiaries. As explained in *Section 3* of this paper, the TP Directive foresees temporary protection to continue for a year and a maximum of three years if the Council decides to prolong it. The EU should have a plan where durable solutions would be available to Ukrainian asylum seekers and refugees if the war continues for a prolonged period.

Art. 3(2)(b) of the [Long-term Residents Directive](#) clarifies that this Directive does not apply to third-country nationals who: ‘are authorised to reside in a Member State on the basis of temporary protection or have applied for authorisation to reside on that basis and are awaiting a decision on their status’. Considering the temporary protection beneficiaries fall outside the

³⁷ Ineli-Ciger, M. (2018), ‘Protecting Syrians in Turkey: A Legal Analysis’, *International Journal of Refugee Law*, Volume 29, Issue 4, December 2017, pp. 555-579.

³⁸ Ineli-Ciger, M. (2018), ‘EU Temporary Protection Directive’, *International Refugee Law Series*, Vol. 10, Brill Nijhoff.

scope of the directive, the EU should tailor long-term policies on how durable solutions can be achieved for Ukrainian refugees in case of a long-lasting conflict.

The third lesson is the need for and importance of responsibility sharing (Ineli-Ciger, 2019³⁹). Turkey, by hosting nearly 4 million refugees and asylum seekers, shouldered the most responsibility in relation to the protection of Syrian refugees throughout the years. It has spent, [according to the Turkish Presidency](#), more than USD 40 billion for the protection of Syrian refugees and in giving Syrians access to education, healthcare, and housing. Although Turkey's effort to improve the protection of Syrians is commendable, many Syrians face serious challenges accessing education, adequate housing, and even minimum basic treatment in the country.⁴⁰ Responsibility-sharing first helps hosting countries to respond better to large scale human displacements and leads to the overall better protection of people in need.

Several EU-funded projects through Facility for Refugees in Turkey and implemented together with Turkish authorities such as [ESSN](#), the [SIHHAT](#) project and [PIKTES](#) have made a visible impact on the protection of Syrians in Turkey and improved their access to social aid, education, and healthcare. That notwithstanding, it is unfortunate that in the case of Turkey, the EU's financial assistance was conditioned to the [2016 EU-Turkey Statement](#) and a clear containment agenda by the EU. Due to the increasing externalisation of EU migration policy, the EU has become more dependent on the cooperation of third country actors, which in turn nurtures its dependency and vulnerability towards the interests of these regimes. A crucial lesson learned is that EU financial assistance on temporary and international protection must not be part of an unfair and inhumane contained mobility approach pursuing migration management goals.

6. Implementing Equal Solidarity

Based on the analysis and lessons learned examined in *Sections 3 to 5* above, this paper calls for the EU to fundamentally rethink the *unequal solidarity paradigm* characterising its asylum and border policies⁴¹ and proposes [two key standards for EU coordinated action based on equal solidarity](#): first, a protection-driven and regularisation standard (Section 6.1); and a non-discrimination standard (Section 6.2). These standards, which draw from international refugee law and human rights law, as well as political commitments in the UN Global Compact on Refugees (GCR) and UN Global Compact on Migration (GCM), and the EU Treaty and secondary legislation obligations, include:

³⁹ Ineli-Ciger, M. (2019), 'The Global Compact on Refugees and Burden Sharing: Will the Compact Address the Normative Gap Concerning Burden Sharing?', *Refugee Survey Quarterly*, Volume 38, Issue 2, June 2019, pp. 115–138.

⁴⁰ Ineli-Ciger, M. and Yigit, O. (2020), 'ASILE Country Fiche Turkey', available at [Country-Fiche Turkey Final Pub.pdf \(asileproject.eu\)](#).

⁴¹ Carrera et al. have argued that 'While solidarity is one of these often-quoted concepts, this notion sometimes pursues or conveys "inter-state responsibility sharing", a "responsibility shifting" agenda and a state-centric understanding and framing of responsibility in relation to international protection". See Carrera, S., Vosyliute, L., Brumat, L. and Feith Tan, N. (2021), *Implementing the United Nations Global Compact on Refugees? Global Asylum Governance and the Role of the European Union*, Migration Policy Centre (MPC) Policy Brief, EUI, Florence, p. 5.

6.1 A protection-driven standard

Temporary protection status should not be substitute or replace the right of beneficiaries to apply for asylum or be regularised in the EU. Therefore, when the time limit of the envisaged EU temporary protection regime ends, it will be crucially important that temporarily protected persons are given the option to choose between access to Refugee Status Determination (RSD) or regularisation, and to envisage the possibility, as enshrined in Objective 7 of the GCM, to 'to facilitate access for migrants in an irregular status to an individual assessment that may lead to regular status'. Moreover, as the Turkish case suggests, it is crucial for the EU to develop a medium and long-term plan to offer Ukrainians and non-Ukrainian nationals fleeing the war durable temporary protection solutions in addition to access to RSD if the war does not end in the near future.

For instance, one possible solution might be to amend the Long-term Residents Directive to include previous temporary protection beneficiaries to its scope (by amending Art 3.2 and 4 of this directive) and include 'the time spent on temporary protection' as 'duration of residence' required under Art. 4 of the Directive. Another option might be to grant *prima facie* refugee/subsidiary protection status to those who are previously protected as temporary protection beneficiaries in addition to amending the Long-term Residents Directive. These are just examples of different mid- and long-term ways forward that can be designed. However, it is crucial that the EU plans ahead and devises different options which do not undermine the 1951 Geneva Convention, preserves the fundamental right to seek asylum and offers temporarily protected persons tangible solutions.

The triggering of the TP Directive also shows that the prevailing EU asylum policy principle where asylum seekers and refugees are excluded from the right to freely move inside the Schengen Area must be reconsidered. The agreed Council Decision expressly allows potential applicants to choose their country of destination to join their families, friends or networks in specific EU Member States. The Commission's proposal has expressly recognised that granting agency to TP potential applicants can be expected to have a positive impact by not overwhelming Member States' asylum systems and reduce pressures on national reception systems. Therefore, the currently applicable EU Dublin Regulation restrictions and criminalisation of so-called 'secondary movements' of asylum seekers and refugees from non-European countries inside the EU should be seriously reconsidered and fully liberalised so as to achieve the same policy goals as the TP Council Decision objectives.

EU Member States that share an EU external border with Ukraine must be supported to ensure they can offer the rights and entitlements foreseen under the TP Directive in an effective and timely manner. Any potential involvement of EU agencies should be mainly focused on a prevailing *asylum-driven approach*, and not one related to border management and policing. In the case that EU agencies' operational support and if deployment by the EUAA or Frontex takes place, a more robust independent fundamental rights monitoring and complaint mechanism of their activities should be ensured and closely monitored during all the

implementation phases. EU agencies should be exclusively deployed *as long as* relevant EU Member States duly comply with their obligations under EU law and towards the fundamental rights of each person. This should be accompanied by an independent evaluation of the experiences emerging from the implementation of the TP Directive.

6.2 A non-discrimination standard

The EU and Member States' responses must fully comply with the prohibition of racial and ethnic discrimination in their borders and asylum policies. Art. 2(2) of the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (ICERD) provides that the States parties should 'undertake to guarantee that the rights enunciated in the present Covenant will be exercised without discrimination of any kind as to race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status'. Art. 1.2 of the ICERD does not in principle apply to distinctions, exclusions, restrictions or preferences made by a State Party to this Convention between citizens and non-citizens.

However, the Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD) has confirmed that this provision must not be interpreted narrowly and interpreted as to also protect non-citizens, including asylum seekers and refugees⁴². The CERD General Recommendation XI noted 'among non-citizens, States parties may not discriminate against any particular nationality⁴³.' The CERD General Recommendation XXII emphasised that, within the general obligation to prohibit and eliminate racial discrimination, States parties should respect the principle of *non-refoulement* – the rights of refugees and displaced persons to return to their homes under conditions of safety⁴⁴. The CERD General Recommendation XXX 'considered that differential treatment based on citizenship or immigration status will constitute discrimination if the criteria for such differentiation, judged in the light of the objectives and purposes of the Convention, are not applied pursuant to a legitimate aim, and are not proportional to the achievement of this aim⁴⁵.' The Committee also mentioned that states should '*ensure that immigration policies do not have the effect of discriminating against persons on the basis of race, colour, descent, or national or ethnic origin*'. Moreover, it is noted in General Recommendation XXX that;

Although some of [the rights listed in Art. 5 of CERD], such as the right to participate in elections, to vote and to stand for election, may be confined to citizens, human rights are, in principle, to be enjoyed by all persons. *States parties are under an obligation to guarantee*

⁴² Skordas, A. and Ineli-Ciger, M., Article 7 1951 Convention in: Zimmermann, A. and Einarsen, T. eds) *The 1951 Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees and its 1967 Protocol A Commentary* (2nd edn, OUP forthcoming) para. 96.

⁴³ CERD, General Recommendation XI on non-citizens, 2003, para. 1. This decision was replaced by CERD Conclusion XXX.

⁴⁴ CERD, *General Recommendation No XXII: Article 5 and refugees and displaced persons*, 1996, para 2; Skordas, Ineli-Ciger, para 96.

⁴⁵ CERD, General Recommendation XXX on discrimination against non-citizens, 2004.

equality between citizens and non-citizens in the enjoyment of these rights to the extent recognized under international law. (Emphasis added).

The outlined progressive interpretation of the CERD was not followed by the 2021 International Court of Justice (ICJ) judgment [Qatar v. United Arab Emirates](#) where the Court decided that the term ‘national origin’ in the ICERD did not include ‘nationality’ and distinctions between citizens and non-citizens did not necessarily violate ICERD. However, this narrow interpretation of the term ‘national origin’ and the Court’s reasoning has been highly criticised. Chiefly, the Court failed to offer any sound reasons [why the CERD’s interpretation was not particularly followed](#).⁴⁶ Furthermore the ICJ completely missed the point that ‘nationality-based discrimination’ often hides or serves as a vessel for racial and religious discrimination and prejudice. While in international law, states are not prohibited from making certain distinctions based on ‘nationality’ however, as noted by Human Rights Committee and cited by Judge Iwasawa in [his separate opinion](#);

a differentiation of treatment is considered to constitute discrimination, unless the criteria for such a differentiation are reasonable and objective; in other words, unless it pursues a *legitimate aim* and there is a *reasonable relationship of proportionality* between the means employed and the aim sought to be achieved.⁴⁷ (Emphasis added).

As the UN Special Rapporteur on contemporary forms of racism, racial discrimination, xenophobia and related intolerance has underlined how the most ‘obvious driver and facilitator of racial discrimination’ in migration and asylum policies is ‘ethno-nationalism’.⁴⁸ The UN Special Rapporteur has also confirmed that laws and policies on migration and asylum ‘must not discriminate, in purpose or effect, on the basis of race, colour, national or ethnic origin’. Although there is no right to be admitted to the territories of a state for asylum seekers under international law, the right to seek asylum is recognised under several human rights treaties as well, as Art. 18 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The EU’s double standards in observing the right to seek asylum and granting international protection indeed breaches the principle of non-discrimination. Thus, there is no place for racial, ethnic or other discrimination, when people are seeking asylum. Any difference in treatment in the context of asylum policies must

⁴⁶ Costello, C. and Foster, M. (2021), ‘Race Discrimination Effaced at the International Court of Justice’, *AJIL Unbound*, 115, pp. 339-344.

⁴⁷ Human Rights Committee, General Comment No. 18 on non-discrimination, 9 Nov. 1989, para. 13; ECtHR, *Biao v. Denmark*, supra note 5, para. 90; IACtHR, Proposed Amendments to the Naturalization Provision of the Constitution of Costa Rica, advisory opinion of 19 Jan. 1984, OC-4/84, para. 57.

⁴⁸ Report of the Special Rapporteur on contemporary forms of racism, racial discrimination, xenophobia and related intolerance (2018)., Racial discrimination in the context of citizenship, nationality and immigration status, 25 April 2018, A/HRC/38/52. In paragraph 40 the Report emphasises that “Ethno-nationalism views the nation as “defined in terms of assumed blood ties and ethnicity”. It has also evolved in the “normalisation and mainstreaming of racist and xenophobic discourse in public discourse...Political parties and leaders have shown increasing and disturbing tolerance for ethno-nationalist messages of hatred and intolerance...”.

be reasonable and objective and, more importantly, justified by states on legitimate grounds, otherwise it amounts to arbitrary discrimination.

The finally adopted text of the Council Decision unlocking the TP regime (in particular its differentiation between Ukrainian nationals and non-nationals) does not seem objective, legally certain and does not apply consistent EU-wide treatment of non-Ukrainian nationals and asylum seekers fleeing Ukraine. This opens up a clear risk of discriminatory treatment during its implementation phases by Member States' authorities.

A comparison between the EU and Member States' responses to the large scale number of entries resulting from the Ukraine War with recent past policies and debates dealing with people fleeing conflicts in Libya, Syria or Afghanistan reveals a stark contradiction with the lack of political support by some EU Member States over the Commission and European Parliament's proposals for reforming the EU asylum system in 2015/2016.⁴⁹ They also show the existence of latent structural discrimination as a key factor characterising what is 'realistic' or not in EU asylum and migration policies. The extreme right narrative and anti-migration agenda have made their way for far too long in both national and EU mainstream policy debates on refugees and migration policies, as well as what is deemed as politically 'realistic' or not.

For instance, the question of discrimination behind the Polish and Hungarian governments' opposition to the [2015 Council Decision on relocation quotas](#) was part of the Court of Justice of the European Union's (CJEU) reasoning which found them in violation of their obligations under EU law. In the Joined Cases [C-643/15](#) and [C-647/15](#), *Slovak Republic and Hungary (supported by Poland) v. Council of the EU* of September 2017, the Polish and Hungarian governments challenged the legality of the 2015 Relocation Decision on the basis that binding quotas would have 'disproportionate effects' as they conceived themselves as 'Member States which are "virtually ethnically homogeneous, like Poland" and whose populations are different, from a cultural and linguistic point of view, from the migrants to be relocated on their territory'⁵⁰.

The Court rejected their argument on the basis of two main grounds: first, making conditional relocation based on 'the existence of cultural or linguistic ties between each applicant for international protection and the Member State' would make it impossible to work in practice; and secondly, crucially, 'considerations relating to the ethnic origin of applicants for international protection cannot be taken into account since they are clearly contrary to EU law and, in particular, to Art. 21 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union'. Therefore, the CJEU confirmed that discriminatory or racist asylum policies by EU Member States are contrary to EU law and are unacceptable in the Union's legal system. It is therefore

⁴⁹ For a similar argument refer to İneli Ciğer, M. (2022), '5 Reasons Why: Understanding the reasons behind the activation of the Temporary Protection Directive in 2022', available at eumigrationlawblog.eu, EU Migration and Asylum Law and Policy, Brussels.

⁵⁰ Para. 302 of the ruling.

of central importance for EU asylum policy to consider institutionalised forms of discrimination or racism towards some asylum seekers not originating from European countries as clear examples of threats to the rule of law as enshrined in Article 2 TEU.

7. Conclusions: Equal solidarity in EU asylum policy

The immediate activation of the Temporary Protection (TP) Directive regime for dealing with the large-scale movement of people fleeing the war in Ukraine is a very positive step to ensuring solidarity and compassion towards those who are suffering and in need of protection. The finally agreed EU temporary protection regime however raises key questions which call for careful consideration and reflection, and which bring us back to the very foundations and working parameters of the EU's asylum policy, chiefly the so-called EU solidarity principle.

The EU and Member States' responses to the people escaping from violence in Ukraine have made the flaws characterizing the unequal solidarity paradigm of current and previous policies covering non-European third country nationals seeking asylum and refugeehood in the Union plainly clear for all to see. The documented cases of discrimination, racism and xenophobia experienced by black Africans, Indian nationals, Pakistani nationals, people of Middle Eastern descent and others, and the statements by some EU national leaders, reveal the existence of structural or institutionalised forms of discrimination concerning the fundamental right to seek asylum and receive protection in the EU.

This can be expected to be exacerbated by the way in which the TP Council Decision follows the consistent approach defended by Member States' governments in countries such as Poland and Hungary to not accept people seeking asylum who are deemed as not 'culturally or ethnically' similar to their own nationals. The Council Decision leaves ample room of manoeuvre for Member States possessing an EU external border to consistently not apply the TP regime and instead provide other 'national responses' which may not ensure equal rights and dignity in comparison to those granted to Ukrainian nationals, people with refugee status and their families. Furthermore, the envisaged TP model does not ensure equal inter-state solidarity either due to not unlocking the inter-state solidarity or quasi-relocation regime of transfers of applicants envisaged in the TP Directive.

Once the EU temporary protection regime is over and temporary protection beneficiaries are given access to RSD, provided that the conflict in Ukraine is still ongoing, most temporary protection beneficiaries would likely qualify for international protection, if not through refugee status then through subsidiary protection status. The implementation phases of the newly established TP regime will be of central importance for ensuring Member States respect their legal commitments under the directive, as well as other relevant pieces of EU asylum law, including the EU Qualifications Directive and every person's right to seek asylum without discrimination and irrespective of status. It will be equally important to monitor the reception

conditions and practical access to rights by TP beneficiaries, and the existence of meaningful and effective ways for them to later choose to apply for asylum and/or regularisation of their status in the medium and longer term.

The EU responses to the war in Ukraine and the refugees fleeing the country show the need to rethink the EU concept of 'solidarity' to address the endemic racism and discrimination that characterises the migration and asylum debate in the EU. It is time to rethink solidarity, from a notion which has been mainly informed for too long by nationalistic and discriminatory government agendas and understood as inter-state responsibility shifting, towards one which places the intersection between fundamental rights, the rule of law and democracy at its centre, and where individuals or a human-centric approach prevails for the sake of decent humanity and justice.